

DIRECTIONS

A newsletter of the Data Documentation Initiative

As we begin 2013, big changes are on the horizon for DDI, including the move to a model-driven specification. In October, several members of the DDI community attended a workshop at Schloss Dagstuhl to jumpstart this work. We are also aligning this work with the new Generic Statistical Information Model (GSIM), which has great potential for DDI. Best wishes to all for a great 2013!

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

Work on Model-Driven DDI Launched

During its [June 2012 meeting](#) in Washington, DC, the DDI Alliance agreed to move forward to develop a model-driven, next-generation DDI specification that could be expressed in a variety of technical formats.

To facilitate this work, a [week-long seminar](#) was held at Schloss Dagstuhl, Leibniz Center for Informatics, in Wadern, Germany. Organized by Arofan Gregory (Open Data Foundation), Wendy Thomas (Population Center, University of Minnesota), Mary Vardigan (University of Michigan - ICPSR), and Joachim Wackerow (GESIS), the seminar drew on expertise from within the DDI Alliance and outside of it, with 21 invited participants contributing to the work.

Progress towards the model was made in both substantive and technical terms. A paper reflecting the Dagstuhl discussions and defining the approach to modeling will be available soon.

Progress was also made at Dagstuhl in a separate [workshop on Semantic Statistics](#), focused on moving DDI into the Linked Data world. You can learn more about the outcomes of both Dagstuhl workshops in these [slides](#).

Sign at Schloss Dagstuhl

New Member Joins Alliance

The DDI Alliance is pleased to welcome a new member – [University of Toronto Libraries](#). Berenica Vejvoda will serve as the Expert Committee Representative.

DDI Alliance to Collaborate on GSIM Development

The DDI Alliance is having discussions with the developers of the [Generic Statistical Information Model \(GSIM\)](#) about a collaboration in which the Alliance will work with GSIM to develop underlying metadata structures for implementation of the higher-level GSIM conceptual model.

This would be of benefit to both groups. GSIM needs an implementation model to serve as a foundation for tools and the Alliance itself is now working on a model-driven specification and can align with much of what GSIM has done. In terms of content, the GSIM model includes some areas that the DDI needs to cover to augment its lifecycle coverage.

The DDI Steering Committee has enthusiastically endorsed such a collaboration. The

Alliance sent Joachim Wackerow and Mari Kleemola to a workshop of the [High-Level Group for the Modernisation of Statistical Production and Services](#) (HLG, the group supporting GSIM development) on November 7-8, 2012, in Geneva, and Achim attended an additional event specifically focused on GSIM the next day. Since that time Achim and Mary Vardigan have met with members of the HLG Secretariat about ways to move the collaboration forward. In December the [SDMX/DDI Dialogue Core Group](#) set up a Task Team to review work on mappings between GSIM and SDMX, and GSIM and DDI. The mapping work will be done by Arofan Gregory and Chris Nelson early in 2013.

Call for Papers for NADDI Announced

The first ever [North American DDI Users Conference](#) will take place on April 2 and 3, with an opening night reception on April 1, at the University of Kansas in Lawrence, Kansas. NADDI is based on the successful European DDI User Conference (EDDI), now in its fourth year. Funding from a Sloan grant will help to support the meeting costs.

The NADDI2013 call for papers is now open. To submit a proposal for a presentation, please fill out the [proposal form](#). The deadline for submissions is January 11, 2013.

Suggestions for presentations related to DDI include the use

Attendees at the Dagstuhl workshop on “DDI Moving Forward” held in October 2012 in Wadern, Germany.

of DDI in research settings, archives, or in official statistics organizations; papers on DDI tools; or critiques of DDI. Of particular interest are presentations on the use of DDI by research teams.

The NADDI Keynote Speaker will be [Dr. Jay Greenfield](#) of Booz Allen Hamilton. Greenfield is the semantic architect for a DDI Lifecycle-based metadata system that supports the [National Children's Study \(NCS\)](#).

If you have additional questions about the NADDI conference, please email naddi@ku.edu.

Successful EDDI 2012 Held in Bergen

Hosted by the Norwegian Social Science Data Services (NSD) in Bergen, Norway, [EDDI 2012](#) took place December 3-4, with an opening reception sponsored by the City Council of Bergen. Participants were warmly welcomed to the city.

The [program](#) included 26 presentations, 6 poster/demos, and 4 tutorials. Overall, 70 participants from 15 countries attended EDDI 2012. A meeting devoted to qualitative data drew 13 people, and the developers meeting around 30.

EDDI13 will be hosted by the [Réseau Quetelet](#) in Paris on

December 3-4, 2013, so save this important date!

Workshop Held at SND

The week before EDDI the Swedish National Data Service (SND) hosted a DDI workshop for Swedish researchers and graduate students, led by Wendy Thomas. Among the topics covered were questionnaires, geographical structures, tools, and upcoming changes in DDI Lifecycle.

SND plans to continue to host DDI workshops for Swedish research organizations to promote DDI usage for better documenting the research process.

New Web Site Manager Announced

Olof Olsson, Web/System Developer at the Swedish National Data Service (SND), has taken on the role of managing the DDI Web site. Please feel free to [contact him](#) with ideas for improvements.

Free Colectica for Excel Tool Released

[Colectica for Excel](#) is a new free Excel add-in that describes data files, variables, and code lists directly within the Microsoft Excel application using open standards. Importing SPSS and Stata data into Excel, along with metadata, is also included in the software release. The standardized metadata, which is compliant with DDI Lifecycle, is

EDDI 2012 Keynote Speaker Svein Nordbotten, professor emeritus of information science at the University of Bergen

stored within the Excel files so it will be available to anyone receiving the documented file. Codebooks can also be customized and generated by the tool, and output in PDF, Word, HTML, and XSL-FO formats.

Colectica Version 4 Now Available

[Colectica Version 4](#), under development since the end of 2010, was released this fall. Version 4 has many new features including completely customizable documentation generation, RDF publishing, and a Workflow Service that allows private metadata to stay private and public metadata to be published. Developers can also now access the Colectica SDK source code.

A new version of the Colectica Reader, the [Free DDI Viewer](#), is also available. To see how to use DDI 3 with Colectica, users can check out the extensive [“how to” articles](#).

Sociometrics Makes Catalog DDI-Compliant

[Sociometrics](#), which provides science-based products and data to researchers and practitioners, recently announced that the nearly all datasets in its [Social Science Electronic Data Library \(SSEDL\)](#) now include DDI study-level metadata, so each dataset is

aligned with current data standards in the social sciences, providing more accessible and easier to catalog data.

Project to Enhance ANES and GSS Metadata Launched

Researchers will have access to improved metadata and new tools to search through and analyze the [General Social Survey](#) and the [American National Election Studies](#) under a new joint initiative launched by ICPSR, the independent research organization NORC at the University of Chicago, and several partners.

Supported by a collaborative research grant from the National Science Foundation, [ICPSR](#), the [American National Election Studies](#) program in the Center for Political Studies at UM’s Institute for Social Research, and [NORC](#) will carry out the two-year [“Metadata Portal for the Social Sciences” project](#). Technical support will be provided by [Metadata Technology North America](#) and [Integrated Data Management Services](#).

The first phase of the project will involve bringing the metadata for the existing GSS and ANES datasets up to the DDI standard. For a sample of

the surveys, the project will also capture enhanced metadata on questionnaire flow and variable transformations.

The second part of the project will create a metadata portal to demonstrate prototype tools that can be built with the new structured metadata.

Thirdly, the project will develop new metadata-driven workflows and best practices to capture metadata early in the data production process so that it can be reused across the research lifecycle.

DDI-Driven Dataset Packaging Tool to Be Developed

Metadata Technology North America Inc. (MTNA) is collaborating with NORC at the University of Chicago towards the capture of new metadata and the development of tools to facilitate and automate the preparation and packaging of the National Science Foundation [Survey of Earned Doctorates \(SED\)](#) data. The recently initiated project will leverage the [DDI XML specification](#) and extend upon [the OpenMetadata Framework \(OMF\)](#) to develop new tools for preparing and submitting the survey outputs to the NSF National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics (NCSES) data repository.